

Dual-branch semi-supervised patch learning for laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma detection in endoscopic images

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Squamous cell carcinoma
Endoscopic imaging
Medical image analysis
Semi-supervised learning
Computer-aided diagnosis

ABSTRACT

Early detection of laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) is critical for improving prognosis and preserving laryngeal function. In routine clinical practice, outpatient endoscopic examinations performed using white light (WL) and narrow-band imaging (NBI) are widely used to detect vocal fold lesions, but visual examinations can be challenging due to subtle lesion appearance or variability in imaging conditions. While deep learning-based SCC detection methods have shown promising results, their training often depends on large labeled datasets that are not always available due to annotation constraints. Consequently, current approaches do not fully exploit information encoded in large, routinely acquired unlabeled data.

In this work, we propose a semi-supervised learning framework for laryngeal SCC detection in endoscopic frames that integrates contrastive representation learning into a single-stage object detection architecture. During training, unlabeled images are processed through a contrastive branch operating on informative patch-level representations extracted from the detection network. By enforcing representation consistency across different augmented views of relevant tissue regions, the proposed strategy encourages the learning of more robust and lesion-aware features under heterogeneous imaging conditions, while preserving a standard inference pipeline without additional supervision.

We evaluated the proposed framework on three datasets collected in two outpatient clinics, comprising 778 endoscopic frames from 79 patients, enabling assessment across different acquisition settings and clinical cohorts.

Experimental results demonstrated consistent improvements over supervised training across all evaluation datasets and imaging modalities. In particular, compared with standard supervised training, the proposed framework improved mAP@0.5 improvements of +5.80, +4.15, and +8.18 points across the three evaluation datasets while also improving Recall across cohorts. These findings suggest that the proposed semi-supervised framework can enhance robustness and generalization in real-world laryngoscopic SCC detection, particularly under heterogeneous acquisition conditions and domain shift.

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1. Introduction

Laryngeal cancer, and in particular squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), represents a major subset of laryngeal malignancies and remains a significant clinical concern due to its impact on voice function, airway integrity, and patient survival [1]. SCC can arise in different anatomical subsites of the larynx, leading to heterogeneous clinical presentations and management strategies. Importantly, early-stage laryngeal cancer is often highly curable, with treatment options that can preserve laryngeal function when diagnosis is achieved at an early stage [1]. In routine clinical practice, laryngeal lesions are primarily evaluated through office-based endoscopic examinations. Technological advances in endoscopic imaging, including improved resolution and optical image-enhancement modalities, have substantially enhanced the visualization of laryngeal mucosa [2]. Flexible transnasal endoscopy, in particular, is widely adopted as it is well tolerated, does not require general anesthesia, and enables rapid and detailed inspection of suspicious lesions in an outpatient setting through both white light (WL) and narrow-band imaging (NBI) modalities [3]. During these examinations, the early detection of lesions that may potentially be SCC is crucial, as suspected malignancies require prompt histopathological confirmation and timely treatment, but challenging due to often subtle mucosal changes [4].

Over the past decade, the surgical data science community has been adopting data-driven methodologies to extract salient information from endoscopic data to provide surgeons with decision support and context awareness [5]. The field of laryngeal SCC screening makes no exception, given the clinical challenges of visual SCC assessment in office-based endoscopy. Hence, there has been growing interest in developing computer-assisted systems to support SCC screening since 2025 [6,7]. Early work shows that convolutional neural network-based features outperform handcrafted texture descriptors in capturing subtle pathological patterns at the image or patch level on the first publicly available dataset in the field [8]. Multi-class classification approaches are proposed in [9] to categorize laryngoscopic images into no vocal folds, normal, and abnormal vocal folds, with the goal of supporting initial screening and assisting clinicians during routine examinations. The evaluation is conducted on a dataset comprising 4549 laryngoscopic images collected from 876 patients at a single clinical center. DenseNet-based architectures are used in [10] to classify benign and malignant laryngeal lesions in laryngoscopic images collected across two medical centers, with experimental evaluation performed on a dataset of 2254 images from 428 patients and including internal and external validation cohorts.

While these classification-based approaches show the potential of deep learning for SCC screening, they do not explicitly localize lesion regions, which limits surgeons' interpretability [11]. To address this limitation, the work in [12] introduces one of the first object detection frameworks for laryngeal lesion analysis, employing a region-based fully convolutional network to enable simultaneous localization and classification of lesions in laryngoscopic images. By formulating the problem as a target detection task, their approach is shown to handle multi-region analysis in complex endoscopic scenes, provided that sufficient annotated training data are available. The experimental evaluation is conducted on a dataset comprising 3223 annotated laryngeal images collected primarily from a single clinical center [12]. The work in [13] proposes the use of YOLOv4 for real-time localization and classification of both malignant and benign vocal cord lesions during routine endoscopy examination in outpatient clinics. Similarly, the work in [14] evaluates multiple convolutional neural network architectures, including YOLO-based detectors, for identifying and classifying various benign lesion types from laryngoscopic images. Their results provide further evidence supporting the effectiveness of single-stage detection architectures in this field. More recent studies explore real-time laryngeal SCC detection from videolaryngoscopy. Single-stage YOLO-based detectors are used to localize SCC lesions in both white-light

and narrow-band imaging video streams, showing inference speeds compatible with real-time clinical use in outpatient settings [15]. The work in [4] introduces a YOLO-based architecture augmented with a super-resolution branch to enhance lesion detection from white-light and narrow-band endoscopic images, while maintaining real-time inference performance suitable for clinical deployment.

All these approaches are based on supervised training, which relies on the availability of a large quantity of annotated data. In clinical practice, the availability of labeled data is often limited due to the high cost and time-consuming nature of expert annotation, which may divert resources from routine clinical activity. As a result, supervised models are usually trained on small or homogeneous datasets and may exhibit limited robustness and reduced generalization when applied to data acquired under different conditions [16]. More importantly, a large amount of information encoded in endoscopic frames acquired routinely is not exploited for model training.

Semi-supervised learning is explored as a potential solution to mitigate the scarcity of annotations in medical imaging [17]. One common approach consists of pseudo-labeling, in which model predictions are reused during training [18,19]. Alternative forms of self-supervision that do not rely on explicit label generation, therefore, are explored. Contrastive representation learning has recently emerged as an effective approach for leveraging unlabeled data in scenarios where expert annotations are limited or unavailable. In this paradigm, models are trained to learn invariant and discriminative representations by contrasting different augmented views of the same image or relevant regions, thereby capturing meaningful visual structure without relying on explicit labels [20,21]. This formulation is typically considered a form of self-supervised or semi-supervised representation learning, depending on whether labeled data are also used during training. In medical image analysis, contrastive learning is adapted by incorporating domain-specific cues, such as anatomical consistency and local structural similarity, enabling robust representation learning even with very few labeled samples [22]. These ideas are explored in ultrasound imaging, for example, to reduce reliance on large annotated datasets for fetal standard-plane identification. In this context, the work in [23] shows that contrastive pretraining or joint contrastive-supervised training can improve classification performance in low-data regimes, particularly for tasks characterized by low inter-class variability, where subtle anatomical differences must be captured reliably. More recent work further shows that contrastive representations can enhance robustness and generalization in the presence of noisy labels and heterogeneous data distributions in ultrasound-based fetal standard plane detection, suggesting their broader applicability to challenging clinical imaging scenarios [24].

Contrastive learning has recently been studied also for laryngeal image analysis tasks. In particular, the study in [25] represents an early attempt to apply contrastive representation learning to narrow-band imaging laryngoscopy under limited annotation settings, based on data collected at a single clinical center. In such work, contrastive training is combined with supervised losses to improve discrimination among multiple lesion categories, leveraging locally cropped patches and pseudo-labels derived from a pretrained backbone network. While this work shows the potential of contrast-based learning to improve representation quality in laryngeal imaging, it remains focused on image-level classification and does not address explicit lesion localization, which is particularly relevant to increase model trustworthiness for diagnostic support. In fact, the adoption of semi-supervised and contrastive learning strategies in laryngeal endoscopy has progressed more slowly than in other medical imaging domains. This can be attributed to the relatively recent application of deep learning to SCC diagnosis and to the historical lack of large and diverse datasets, as available data have typically been collected at single institutions and in limited quantities. Moreover, existing contrastive learning strategies are often based on image-level representation learning or multi-stage pretraining schemes that may not be well suited to real-time endoscopic

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed semi-supervised learning framework. Labeled data are used to optimize the standard YOLO detection loss, while unlabeled data are processed through the shared feature extractor to derive informative patches for contrastive learning. A projection head maps extracted features to a contrastive embedding space and is used only during training. The detection and contrastive losses are combined into a joint, total loss for end-to-end optimization. At inference time, only the YOLO detector is retained.

applications, where lightweight architectures and efficient inference are essential. In endoscopic imaging, lesions frequently occupy only a limited portion of the field of view, while large background regions may dominate global image representations. As a result, enforcing consistency at the image level may reduce the ability of the model to focus on subtle pathological patterns. In this work, we build on these early efforts by leveraging large collections of unlabeled endoscopic data to introduce a semi-supervised learning strategy within a modern object detection framework, developed in the collaborative context of the Horizon Europe project AIRCARE.²

Unlike conventional image-level contrastive learning approaches, the proposed framework performs consistency enforcement directly on informative patch-level representations extracted from detector predictions within a lightweight single-stage detection architecture. In contrast to prior contrastive learning methods for laryngeal image analysis that focus on image-level classification and rely on attention-guided patch extraction or pseudo-label generation [25], the proposed approach integrates contrastive learning directly into the object detection pipeline without introducing additional supervision signals for unlabeled data.

During training, informative regions are automatically identified from intermediate detector predictions, providing approximate lesion localization even in the absence of manual annotations. These regions are then used to generate positive and negative patch pairs for contrastive learning, encouraging consistent representations of clinically relevant tissue patterns.

This patch-level formulation is particularly important in endoscopic imaging, where lesions often occupy only a limited portion of the image while large areas correspond to visually similar anatomical background structures. Enforcing consistency at the image level may therefore bias representation learning toward dominant background appearance rather than subtle pathological cues. By focusing the contrastive objective on localized informative regions, the proposed framework promotes lesion-aware representation learning, improves sensitivity to small pathological patterns, and preserves the computational efficiency and real-time inference capabilities required for clinical endoscopic applications. The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

Table 1

Summary of the datasets used in this study, including modality-specific image counts for the evaluation sets.

Dataset	Split	Patients	Images	WL	NBI	Usage
GOA-1 labeled	Train	207	1547	775	772	Training
	Val	60	485	259	226	Validation
	Test	31	214	117	97	Evaluation
GOA-1 unlabeled	–	158	9815	–	–	Unlabeled training
GOA-2	Test	17	180	81	99	Evaluation
ATH	Test	31	384	192	192	External evaluation

- We propose a semi-supervised learning framework for detecting vocal fold SCC in endoscopic images, integrating contrastive representation learning into a state-of-the-art object detection model.
- We introduce a patch-based contrastive learning strategy tailored to endoscopic imagery, which leverages unlabeled examinations without relying on pseudo-labeling or additional annotations.
- We conduct an ablation study to analyze the impact of key framework design choices, including the epoch at which the contrastive learning is activated during training and the strength of data augmentation.
- We validate the proposed approach on endoscopic image data acquired during routine clinical practice from patients with histologically confirmed SCC, including datasets acquired in two different centers, demonstrating improved generalization under domain shift.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the proposed methodology, including the datasets, the baseline detection model, and the semi-supervised learning framework. Section 4 presents the experimental results and ablation studies. Finally, Section 5 discusses the findings and their implications, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Methods

The overall semi-supervised framework for SCC detection in vocal fold endoscopic images is illustrated in Fig. 1. During training, both labeled and unlabeled endoscopic frames are exploited within a unified optimization pipeline. Labeled images are processed through the YOLO detector and contribute to the supervised detection loss, while unlabeled images are forwarded through the shared backbone

² <https://aircareproject.eu/>.

and an auxiliary contrastive branch. More specifically, the contrastive branch operates on patch-level representations extracted from unlabeled frames. Informative regions are identified directly from detector predictions and used to generate positive and negative patch pairs for contrastive learning. This strategy enables the framework to leverage unlabeled data without relying on pseudo-label generation, while encouraging consistent representations of visually relevant tissue regions. The proposed framework extends our previous work based on earlier YOLO architectures by incorporating recent advances in single-stage object detection [4]. In particular, YOLOv11n is adopted to benefit from the architectural and training improvements introduced in recent YOLO versions, while maintaining the efficiency and real-time inference capabilities required in clinical endoscopic applications [26].

YOLOv11n is a lightweight variant of the Ultralytics YOLOv11 family [27] and follows the standard single-stage detection paradigm, jointly performing object localization and classification within a unified convolutional architecture. The network consists of a backbone for hierarchical feature extraction, a neck for multi-scale feature aggregation, and a detection head predicting bounding box coordinates and class probabilities. Despite its compact design, YOLOv11n preserves multi-scale detection capabilities, enabling localization of lesions with different spatial extents in endoscopic images.

As for the training procedure, let $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 3}$ denote an unlabeled image sampled from the unlabeled dataset. For each unlabeled mini-batch, YOLOv11n is deployed in inference mode and bounding boxes are predicted after standard non-maximum suppression. Since no manual annotations are available for unlabeled images, the detector predictions are used to identify informative regions likely to contain pathological tissue. In particular, the highest-confidence predicted bounding box is selected and used to extract a positive patch p^+ , obtained by cropping the corresponding image region. This strategy encourages the contrastive branch to focus on lesion-aware representations rather than global image appearance. If no detection is produced, the entire image is used as a fallback positive patch. Negative patches p^- are generated through random crops constrained to have minimal spatial overlap with all predicted lesion regions. More specifically, candidate crops are accepted only if their intersection-over-union (IoU) with all predicted boxes remains below a threshold δ . This procedure encourages the contrastive objective to separate informative pathological regions from surrounding anatomical background structures.

For each positive patch \mathbf{p}^+ , two stochastic augmentations are sampled to obtain two correlated views:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_1^+ = t(\mathbf{p}^+), \quad \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_2^+ = t'(\mathbf{p}^+), \quad (1)$$

where $t(\cdot)$ and $t'(\cdot)$ are independently sampled transformations from the same augmentation family. In addition, a single augmented view of the negative patch is generated:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{p}}^- = s(\mathbf{p}^-). \quad (2)$$

Feature representations are extracted by using the first feature extraction layers of the YOLOv11n network, which are shared with the detection task and precede the neck and detection head. These layers, denoted as a mapping $f_\theta(\cdot)$, are applied to the augmented patches to produce feature maps used for contrastive learning:

$$\mathbf{h} = f_\theta(\tilde{\mathbf{p}}) \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times H' \times W'}. \quad (3)$$

A projection head $g_\phi(\cdot)$ maps \mathbf{h} to a d -dimensional embedding space:

$$\mathbf{u} = g_\phi(\mathbf{h}) \in \mathbb{R}^d, \quad (4)$$

implemented as global average pooling followed by a two-layer multi-layer perceptron with batch normalization and ReLU activation. Specifically, the hidden layer has a dimensionality of 4096, mapping to a final embedding space of $d = 1024$. The final embeddings are ℓ_2 -normalized:

$$\mathbf{z} = \frac{\mathbf{u}}{\|\mathbf{u}\|_2}. \quad (5)$$

Given a mini-batch of B unlabeled samples, let $\mathbf{z}_i^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{z}_i^{(2)}$ denote the normalized embeddings of the two augmented views of the positive patch from the i th image. Let \mathbf{z}_j^- denote the embedding of the negative patch associated with the j th image. For each anchor $\mathbf{z}_i^{(1)}$, the positive logit is defined as $\mathbf{z}_i^{(1)} \cdot \mathbf{z}_i^{(2)}$, and the negatives are $\mathbf{z}_i^{(1)} \cdot \mathbf{z}_j^-$ for $j \neq i$. Using a temperature parameter τ , the contrastive loss is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{con} = -\frac{1}{B} \sum_{i=1}^B \log \frac{\exp(\mathbf{z}_i^{(1)} \cdot \mathbf{z}_i^{(2)} / \tau)}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \exp(\mathbf{z}_i^{(1)} \cdot \mathbf{z}_k / \tau)}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(i)$ denotes the set consisting of the positive embedding $\mathbf{z}_i^{(2)}$ and all negative embeddings in the mini-batch. This formulation enforces representation consistency by encouraging embeddings derived from different augmented views of the same informative patch to remain close in the latent space, while simultaneously pushing apart representations associated with unrelated background regions or different samples within the mini-batch.

The overall training objective jointly optimizes the supervised detection and contrastive learning objectives:

$$\mathcal{L}_{total} = \mathcal{L}_{det} + \alpha(e) \mathcal{L}_{con}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathcal{L}_{det} denotes the standard YOLO detection loss. The contrastive term is activated after a contrastive activation delay of E_{start} epochs. The weighting factor $\alpha(e)$ is defined as:

$$\alpha(e) = \begin{cases} 0, & e < E_{start}, \\ \alpha_{max} \min\left(\frac{e - E_{start}}{E_{ramp}}, 1\right), & e \geq E_{start}, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

with $\alpha_{max} = 0.8$, $E_{start} = 40$, and $E_{ramp} = 5$. The projection head parameters ϕ are optimized using AdamW with a learning rate of 5×10^{-4} , while the detector parameters θ are updated using the standard Ultralytics optimization procedure, with the contrastive loss incorporated through \mathcal{L}_{total} .

Following standard practice in contrastive representation learning, the projection head is used only during training and is discarded at inference time. All evaluations are performed using the original YOLOv11n detection architecture. The overall training procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1.

2.1. Multicentric data preparation

In this study, we consider three datasets derived from a patient cohort that encompasses individuals aged between 30 and 94 years, with a demographic distribution of 85% male and 15% female. These datasets are detailed as follows and summarized in Table 1. In particular, the GOA-1 dataset comprises both labeled and unlabeled endoscopic frames collected from the same patient cohort, while GOA-2 and ATH are used exclusively for evaluation. Representative examples are shown in Fig. 2. The data used in this study may be provided upon request to the authors, pending approval by the AIRCARE consortium and compliance with legal constraints.

2.1.1. GOA-1 dataset

The GOA-1 dataset consists of endoscopic images of vocal folds affected by SCC, collected by clinical partners at the Otolaryngology Unit of San Martino Hospital (Genova, Italy) between June 2020 and August 2022. Endoscopic video recordings were acquired during routine outpatient examinations using a high-definition flexible transnasal nasopharyngolaryngoscope (HD Video Rhino-laryngoscope Olympus ENF-VH, Olympus Medical System Corporation, Tokyo, Japan), following standard clinical practice. We received approval from the local Institutional Review Board (CER Liguria: 169/2022) to use the dataset for this study.

Fig. 2. Example endoscopic frames illustrating visual variability across the datasets used in this study (rows: GOA-1 labeled, GOA-1 unlabeled, GOA-2, ATH; six randomly sampled frames per dataset).

Algorithm 1: Semi-supervised training procedure with contrastive learning.

Input : number of epochs E , contrastive start epoch E_{start} ,
 labeled dataloader D_{lab} , unlabeled dataloader D_{unlab} ,
 YOLO detector $\mathcal{M}(\cdot)$ with feature extractor $f(\cdot)$,
 projection head $g(\cdot)$, contrastive weight schedule $\alpha(\cdot)$

Output: trained YOLO detector $\mathcal{M}(\cdot)$

```

for  $e \leftarrow 1$  to  $E$  do
  foreach  $mini\text{-batch } (x^{lab}, y^{lab}) \sim D_{lab}$  do
     $y^{pred} \leftarrow \mathcal{M}(x^{lab})$ ;
     $L_{det} \leftarrow L_{sup}(y^{pred}, y^{lab})$ ;
    if  $e \geq E_{start}$  then
       $x^{unlab} \sim D_{unlab}$ ;
       $(p^+, p^-) \leftarrow \text{PatchMining}(\mathcal{M}, x^{unlab})$ ;
       $\tilde{p}_1^+, \tilde{p}_2^+ \leftarrow \text{Augment}(p^+)$ ;
       $\tilde{p}^- \leftarrow \text{Augment}(p^-)$ ;
       $z_1^+ \leftarrow g(f(\tilde{p}_1^+))$ ;
       $z_2^+ \leftarrow g(f(\tilde{p}_2^+))$ ;
       $z^- \leftarrow g(f(\tilde{p}^-))$ ;
       $L_{con} \leftarrow L_{con} + \alpha(e) L_{con}(z_1^+, z_2^+, z^-)$ ;
    else
       $L_{con} \leftarrow 0$ ;
     $L \leftarrow L_{det} + \alpha(e) L_{con}$ ;
    Update parameters of  $\mathcal{M}$  and  $g$  using  $\nabla L$ ;
  return  $\mathcal{M}(\cdot)$ 

```

2.1.1.1. Labeled subset. The labeled subset of GOA-1 includes endoscopic frames manually annotated by expert clinicians with at least five years of experience in laryngology. For each patient, multiple representative frames, typically between 2 and 10, are selected from the same endoscopic examination, including both WL and NBI modalities. Only frames of adequate diagnostic quality are retained, while images affected by motion blur, saliva artifacts, or insufficient visualization of the vocal folds are excluded. All images in the dataset are acquired from patients with histologically confirmed SCC. Pathological regions are

delineated through tight bounding boxes enclosing the visible lesion, and annotations are gathered and exported in the standard COCO format using a custom annotation software. The annotation process follows a consistent protocol across all images.

The dataset is split into training, validation, and test sets at the patient level to prevent data leakage across splits. The training set includes 1547 images from 207 patients, the validation set includes 485 images from 60 patients, and the test set includes 214 images from 31 patients. The number of frames per patient is comparable across splits (training: 7.47 ± 2.80 , validation: 7.92 ± 2.53 , test: 6.90 ± 2.45), ensuring a balanced representation of patient examinations. Both WL and NBI modalities are represented in all subsets, with an approximately balanced distribution in the training set (50.1% WL, 49.9% NBI) and a mild predominance of WL images in the validation and test sets. Image resolution varies across the dataset, with widths ranging from 308 to 1632 pixels and heights from 576 to 1072 pixels. To the best of our knowledge, this labeled collection represents one of the largest annotated datasets for laryngeal SCC endoscopy reported to date in terms of patient count.

2.1.1.2. Unlabeled subset. The unlabeled subset of the GOA-1 dataset is derived from the same endoscopic video recordings and patient cohort as the labeled data and consists of frames that were not manually annotated. All unlabeled frames are extracted exclusively from videos associated with patients already present in the supervised training set, and no additional patients or external video sources are considered.

Given the high frame rate of the recordings (30 frames per second), frames are sampled at a fixed temporal interval of 25 frames, corresponding to an effective sampling rate of roughly 1 frame per second. For each temporal window, frame quality is automatically assessed using a pre-trained convolutional neural network, originally proposed in [28], and exported in ONNX format. The network is designed to identify visually informative frames based on image quality criteria such as motion blur or exposure. Importantly, the model does not perform semantic analysis or evaluate the presence of anatomical structures or pathological findings. Only frames classified as informative by the quality assessment model are retained. Following the automatic filtering step, all extracted frames are manually reviewed, and images not displaying vocal folds are discarded. To further limit patient-specific

redundancy and promote a more balanced representation across subjects, the maximum number of retained unlabeled frames per patient is capped at 80 images. The resulting unlabeled dataset comprises 9815 images from 158 patients, with an average of 62.12 ± 19.06 images per patient. Image resolution is heterogeneous, with widths ranging from 468 to 1760 pixels and heights from 386 to 1072 pixels.

No lesion annotations or imaging modality labels (WL or NBI) are available for this dataset. No unlabeled data overlap with validation or test patients, thereby preventing information leakage during model evaluation. The unlabeled images are used solely for contrastive representation learning and do not contribute to supervised loss computation or performance evaluation.

2.1.2. Prospective clinical study (GOA-2)

Although GOA-2 is acquired within a prospective clinical study, it is used retrospectively for evaluation in this work. It comprises a cohort of endoscopic images of vocal folds affected by SCC, acquired at the Otolaryngology Department of San Martino Hospital (Genova, Italy) from July 2024. Data acquisition, frame selection, and annotation protocols are identical to those adopted for the GOA-1 (both labeled and unlabeled) dataset.

At the time of this study, the GOA-2 dataset comprises 180 images from 17 patients. Multiple frames are selected per patient from the same endoscopic examination, with an average of 10.59 ± 4.45 images per patient (minimum 1, maximum 24). Image resolution is heterogeneous, with widths ranging from 440 to 1720 pixels and heights from 480 to 1072 pixels, reflecting variability in acquisition and cropping procedures.

Unlike the GOA-1 dataset, GOA-2 is being collected progressively during routine clinical activity. The dataset is used exclusively for evaluation, to assess the performance of the proposed method on prospectively acquired clinical data. No GOA-2 images are used during training, validation, or model selection. This evaluation enables a more realistic assessment of model behavior in routine clinical practice.

We received approval to use the dataset for this study from the local Institutional Review Board (N. CET - Liguria: 508/2023).

2.1.3. External dataset (ATH)

An independent external dataset, referred to as ATH, is used exclusively for external evaluation to assess model generalization across acquisition settings. The dataset consists of endoscopic images of vocal folds affected by SCC, collected at the Otolaryngology Unit of the Oncologic Hospital Saint Savvas (Athens, Greece) with local Ethics Committee approval. All images are acquired during standard clinical procedures using a flexible or rigid high-definition video endoscope (Olympus).

The ATH dataset includes a total of 384 images from 31 patients, with an average of 12.39 ± 14.28 images per patient (minimum 1, maximum 50). Images depict pathological vocal folds only, and all patients are diagnosed with SCC. Annotations in the form of bounding boxes are provided for all images following the same labeling protocol adopted for the GOA-1 dataset. Image resolution ranges from 756 to 1728 pixels in width and 756 to 1080 pixels in height.

The ATH dataset is not used during training or model selection and serves solely as an external test set. No patients or images from ATH overlap with the GOA-1 labeled or unlabeled datasets.

3. Experimental protocol

A series of experiments was conducted to evaluate the proposed semi-supervised learning framework and to assess its generalization capability. All experiments are based on the YOLOv11n detector and the training procedures described in Section 2.

With reference to the hyperparameters defined in Section 2, the contrastive activation delay and augmentation strength were determined

through the ablation study detailed in Section 3.1. The remaining parameters were selected via grid search by choosing the configuration that minimized the validation loss. Specifically, we experimentally set the IoU threshold for negative patch selection to $\delta = 0.1$, the maximum contrastive weight to $\alpha_{max} = 0.8$, and the temperature parameter to $\tau = 0.1$. Furthermore, features for contrastive learning were extracted from the first $L = 12$ layers of the YOLOv11n backbone. These mid-level feature maps contain semantic information beneficial for distinguishing lesions from normal tissue while maintaining sufficient spatial resolution for patch-level comparison, and were jointly trained with the contrastive branch.

3.1. Ablation study

An ablation study was conducted to analyze the impact of key design choices in the proposed semi-supervised framework. In particular, we investigated the effect of the contrastive activation delay, i.e., the training epoch at which the contrastive branch is activated, and the influence of the data augmentation strength used in the contrastive branch. Unless otherwise specified, all other training parameters were kept identical to the reference semi-supervised configuration described in Section 2.

- *Contrastive activation delay (Act_delay)* The contrastive loss is not applied from the beginning of training, but is activated after an initial supervised phase to allow the detector to learn stable object detection. To evaluate the effect of this design choice, we varied the contrastive activation delay E_{start} , defined as the number of initial epochs during which only the supervised detection loss is optimized. The values of 15, 20, 40, and 60 epochs for E_{start} were evaluated. In all configurations, once activated, the contrastive loss weight was ramped linearly for $E_{ramp} = 5$ epochs up to its maximum value $\alpha_{max} = 0.8$, as defined in Section 2.
- *Data augmentation strength ($Aug_strength$)* To study the effect of augmentation strength on the proposed contrastive learning scheme, three augmentation tiers were defined, denoted as Tier A, Tier B, and Tier C, corresponding respectively to *soft*, *mild*, and *strong* augmentation regimes. The three tiers comprise the same set of transformation operators but differ in the magnitude and probability with which these transformations are applied to the images. Tier A applies relatively conservative geometric and photometric perturbations and is designed to preserve most of the original image appearance, resulting in augmented views that remain closely aligned with the source patch. Tier B represents an intermediate configuration and is used as the reference setting in the main experiments. Tier C applies substantially stronger transformations, producing more aggressive appearance variations while still preserving the underlying anatomical structure. The specific parameter ranges associated with each augmentation tier are summarized in Table 2. Unless otherwise stated, all semi-supervised experiments adopt Tier B, while Tiers A and C are evaluated exclusively within the ablation study to assess the sensitivity of the contrastive learning process to augmentation strength.
- *Contrastive learning as a standalone pretraining strategy ($Contr_pretrain$)* We further investigated whether contrastive learning could be effectively used as a standalone pretraining strategy for the YOLO backbone, followed by standard supervised fine-tuning. In this setting, the first 12 layers, for fair comparison, of the detector were pretrained using contrastive learning only, without any detection objective, and the resulting weights were then used to initialize the supervised YOLOv11n training.

Table 2
Augmentation strength tiers used in the contrastive learning branch.

Parameter	Tier A	Tier B	Tier C
Crop scale	[0.6, 1.0]	[0.3, 1.0]	[0.2, 1.0]
Flip prob.	0.3	0.5	0.7
Color jitter	Weak	Medium	Strong
Blur σ	[0.05, 0.8]	[0.1, 2.0]	[0.2, 3.0]
Affine (deg)	$\pm 7^\circ$	$\pm 15^\circ$	$\pm 20^\circ$
Color-affine	Weak	Medium	Strong

3.2. Comparison with supervised training

The supervised baseline detector (*Sup_baseline*) was trained using the Ultralytics implementation of YOLOv11n [27] on the GOA-1 labeled dataset described in 2.1.1.1. Following the same protocol, we also compared the proposed semi-supervised framework with YOLOv5 and YOLOv8, which have been used in the literature for laryngeal lesion analysis [4,15,29]. In all experiments, input images were resized to 640×640 pixels, and the network was initialized using weights pre-trained on the COCO dataset. The detection architecture was configured for single-class object detection, where the target class corresponds to squamous cell carcinoma lesions of the vocal folds. The model was trained for 150 epochs using a batch size of 64 and a fixed random seed to ensure reproducibility. Optimization was carried out using the AdamW optimizer with an initial learning rate of 5×10^{-4} . A cosine learning rate schedule was employed, with the terminal learning rate set to 0.01 times the initial value. Validation was performed during training, and early stopping was enabled with a patience of 30 epochs. Model checkpoints were saved every 5 epochs.

3.3. Evaluation metrics

Model performance was evaluated using standard object detection metrics computed on the test sets. All metrics were computed using the Ultralytics evaluation pipeline with default settings unless otherwise specified. Detection accuracy was assessed using the mean Average Precision (mAP) at fixed intersection-over-union (IoU) thresholds. In particular, we report mAP_{50} and mAP_{75} , corresponding to IoU thresholds of 0.5 and 0.75, respectively, following common practice in recent works on laryngeal lesion detection [4,15]. These metrics quantify detection performance under progressively stricter localization requirements. Precision and recall were reported to characterize the balance between false positive and false negative detections. Precision is defined as the proportion of predicted bounding boxes that correctly correspond to annotated lesions, while recall measures the proportion of annotated lesions that are successfully detected by the model. All metrics were computed at the image level using bounding box annotations as ground truth. For external evaluation on the ATH dataset, the same evaluation protocol and metrics were applied without any dataset-specific tuning, ensuring a fair assessment of cross-dataset generalization.

3.4. Implementation details

Unless otherwise specified, the semi-supervised training procedure followed the reference configuration described in Section 2, with selected design choices guided by the ablation study reported in Section 3.1.

All models were implemented in Python using the Ultralytics framework for YOLOv11 and PyTorch for custom components. Training and evaluation were performed using PyTorch with CUDA acceleration. Unless otherwise specified, all experiments followed the default Ultralytics training and evaluation configurations.

For reproducibility, a fixed random seed was used across all experiments. Model checkpoints were saved periodically during training, and

final evaluation results were obtained using the checkpoint corresponding to the best validation performance, as selected automatically by the training framework.

All custom components introduced for the semi-supervised framework, including the projection head and contrastive loss computation, were implemented using standard PyTorch modules and integrated into the Ultralytics training loop via callback functions.

Experiments were executed on an HPC cluster using a single NVIDIA A100-SXM4 GPU with 80 GB of memory. CUDA version 12.8 and NVIDIA driver version 570.86.10 were used. Automatic mixed precision (AMP) was enabled during training to improve computational efficiency and memory utilization.

4. Results

This section presents the experimental results obtained with the proposed semi-supervised learning framework. Ablation studies, which were conducted to analyze the impact of key design choices in the proposed method, are presented first. We then compare the performance of the supervised baseline and the semi-supervised model across different datasets to assess robustness and generalization.

4.1. Ablation study results

Ablation experiments were conducted on the GOA-1 labeled test set to evaluate the influence of specific components of the proposed framework. In particular, we analyzed the effect of the contrastive activation delay and the strength of data augmentation applied in the contrastive learning branch. Unless otherwise specified, all other training parameters were kept identical to the reference configuration described in Section 3. The results of the ablation study are summarized in Table 3.

Effect of contrastive activation delay (Act_{delay}): This experiment evaluated the impact of the contrastive activation delay E_{start} on detection performance. Different values of E_{start} were considered, corresponding to the number of initial epochs during which only the supervised detection loss was optimized before enabling contrastive learning. The results of this ablation study are summarized in Table 3. Varying E_{start} resulted in different performance levels across all evaluation metrics. Among the evaluated configurations, the reference setting ($E_{start} = 40$) achieved the highest $mAP@0.5$ and $mAP@0.75$ values, together with the highest recall. Earlier activation of the contrastive branch ($E_{start} = 15$ and 20) yielded lower mAP values, while delaying activation to $E_{start} = 60$ resulted in reduced performance compared to the reference configuration.

Effect of augmentation strength ($Aug_{strength}$): Table 3 also reports detection performance for different augmentation strengths applied in the contrastive learning branch. Results are shown for soft (Tier A), mild (Tier B), and strong (Tier C) augmentation settings, with the contrastive activation delay fixed to $E_{start} = 40$. The mild augmentation setting (Tier B) achieved the highest $mAP@0.5$ and $mAP@0.75$ values. Both softer and stronger augmentations resulted in lower performance on at least one of the reported metrics, with the strong augmentation setting (Tier C) showing reduced precision compared to the reference configuration.

Effect of contrastive learning as a standalone pretraining strategy ($Contr_{pretrain}$): As shown in Table 4, contrastive learning applied as a standalone pretraining strategy followed by supervised fine-tuning results in a consistently lower detection performance compared to the proposed joint semi-supervised framework across all evaluated datasets. On the GOA-1 test set, contrastive pretraining achieves an $mAP@0.5$ of 62.57, compared to 71.27 obtained with the proposed approach, while also resulting in lower precision and recall. More pronounced performance gaps are observed on the GOA-2 and ATH datasets, where $mAP@0.5$ values decrease from 57.06 to 43.70 and from 54.30 to 30.78, respectively, when using contrastive pretraining instead of the proposed joint training strategy.

Table 3
Ablation study results on the GOA-1 labeled test set for the proposed framework.

Setting	Configuration	mAP@0.5	mAP@0.75	Precision	Recall
Contrastive activation delay (<i>Act_delay</i>)	$E_{\text{start}} = 15$	69.42	29.88	79.66	59.57
	$E_{\text{start}} = 20$	70.72	29.95	75.35	66.47
	$E_{\text{start}} = 40$ (ref.)	71.27	32.84	75.26	67.39
	$E_{\text{start}} = 60$	68.71	30.94	72.68	64.76
Augmentation strength (<i>Aug_strength</i>)	Tier A (soft)	70.80	29.10	73.23	69.00
	Tier B (mild, ref.)	71.27	32.84	75.26	67.39
	Tier C (strong)	66.94	29.49	67.49	67.90

Fig. 3. Qualitative comparison between supervised and semi-supervised SCC detection across datasets and imaging modalities. For each dataset (rows: GOA-1 labeled, GOA-2, ATH) and modality (columns: white light (WL) and narrow-band imaging (NBI)), three representative examples are shown. Each example is visualized as a triptych showing, from left to right, the ground-truth annotation (■), the prediction of the supervised baseline (■), and the prediction of the proposed semi-supervised model (■). Only the highest-confidence prediction is displayed for each model. The qualitative results highlight improved lesion localization and robustness of the semi-supervised approach, particularly in challenging cases and under domain shift.

4.2. Comparison with state-of-the-art methods

We next compared the proposed semi-supervised learning framework with the *Sup_baseline* and the results are reported in Table 5a. Representative qualitative detection examples are shown in Fig. 3. On the GOA-1 labeled test set, the semi-supervised model achieved higher mAP@0.5 and mAP@0.75 values compared to the supervised baseline, together with higher precision and recall. On the GOA-2 dataset, the semi-supervised model achieved higher mAP@0.5, mAP@0.75, and recall values than the supervised baseline, while precision values were comparable between the two models. On the external ATH dataset,

results reported in Table 5a show that our semi-supervised framework achieved higher mAP@0.5 and mAP@0.75 values than the supervised baseline, together with an increase in recall, while precision values were similar across the two approaches.

Detection performance was further analyzed separately for white-light (WL) and narrow-band imaging (NBI) images on the test sets. Table 6 reports modality-specific results for supervised and semi-supervised training across the evaluated datasets. On the GOA-1 labeled test set, the semi-supervised model achieves higher mAP@0.5 and recall than the supervised baseline for both WL and NBI images, with consistent improvements observed across metrics. On the ATH dataset,

Table 4

Ablation study comparing contrastive pretraining followed by fine-tuning (*Contr_pretrain*) with the proposed joint semi-supervised framework (*Proposed*).

Dataset	Model	mAP@0.5	mAP@0.75	Precision	Recall
GOA-1	<i>Contr_pretrain</i>	62.57	27.19	63.87	60.87
	Proposed framework	71.27	32.84	75.26	67.39
ATH	<i>Contr_pretrain</i>	30.78	6.57	39.30	38.36
	Proposed framework	54.30	14.21	64.38	50.22
GOA-2	<i>Contr_pretrain</i>	43.70	17.43	65.13	36.78
	Proposed framework	57.06	29.53	64.27	51.81

Table 5

Overall comparison between the supervised baseline and the proposed semi-supervised approach.

(a) Quantitative analysis of object detection performance across different datasets. Statistically significant improvements ($p < 0.05$) with respect to the supervised baseline, assessed using a paired permutation test on the main evaluation metrics, are marked with an asterisk (*).

Dataset	Model	mAP@0.5	mAP@0.75	Precision	Recall
GOA-1 labeled	<i>Sup_baseline</i>	65.47	27.22	70.06	60.43
	Proposed framework	71.27*	32.84*	75.26*	67.39*
ATH	<i>Sup_baseline</i>	46.12	12.35	64.52	40.31
	Proposed framework	54.30*	14.21	64.38	50.22*
GOA-2	<i>Sup_baseline</i>	52.91	29.15	66.51	45.60
	Proposed framework	57.06	29.53	64.27	51.81

(b) Comparison of model complexity and training time requirements.

Model	Parameters (M)	GFLOPs	Training time (s)
<i>Sup_baseline</i>	2.59	6.40	2100
Proposed framework	7.85	6.41	5140

semi-supervised training results in higher mAP@0.5 and recall for both imaging modalities, while precision values remain comparable between the two approaches. On the GOA-2 dataset, the semi-supervised model shows higher recall for both WL and NBI images, with mAP values comparable to or higher than those obtained with supervised training.

In addition to detection performance, [Table 5b](#) reports a computational cost analysis for both models. As expected, the proposed semi-supervised framework requires a higher number of parameters during training (7.85 M vs. 2.59 M) and a longer training time (5140 s vs. 2100 s) compared to the supervised baseline, due to the auxiliary contrastive branch. However, because the projection head is entirely discarded after training, the computational cost during inference remains almost identical (6.41 GFLOPs vs. 6.40 GFLOPs).

[Table 7](#) reports a comprehensive comparison of the proposed framework against established state-of-the-art object detectors. The baselines include fully supervised CNN-based models (YOLOv5, YOLOv8), fully supervised Transformer-based models (RT-DETR [30], DINO-DETR [31]), and a widely adopted semi-supervised method based on pseudo-labeling (Unbiased Teacher [32]). The results show that the proposed framework achieves the highest mAP@0.5 on the GOA-1 (71.27) and GOA-2 (57.06) datasets. While transformer-based models like RT-DETR show competitive performance on the in-domain dataset, they exhibit a significant performance drop on the external ATH dataset (30.64 mAP@0.5). Regarding semi-supervised learning, the Unbiased-teacher baseline achieves the highest recall across all datasets (reaching 83.90 on ATH) and the highest mAP@0.5 on the external ATH dataset (60.96).

5. Discussion

In this work, we investigated a semi-supervised learning framework for detecting laryngeal SCC in endoscopic images, aiming to exploit unlabeled clinical data routinely acquired during outpatient examinations. The proposed approach integrated contrastive representation

Fig. 4. t-SNE visualization of feature representations extracted from a YOLOv11n model pretrained on the COCO dataset. Each point corresponds to an endoscopic image and is colored according to the dataset of origin (GOA-1 labeled, GOA-2, ATH). The separation observed for the ATH dataset reflects differences in acquisition conditions and imaging characteristics, illustrating the presence of domain shift across datasets. The separation of the embedding space into two main groupings is largely due to the imaging modality (WL and NBI).

learning into a lightweight single-stage object detection architecture, YOLOv11n, enabling the joint use of labeled and unlabeled data during training while preserving the same efficient inference pipeline used in standard supervised settings. This design choice is particularly relevant for potential deployment in routine clinical endoscopy, where real-time performance and computational efficiency are essential. In particular, the framework was designed to mitigate the limitations associated with scarce labeled data, which remain a common challenge in laryngeal endoscopic imaging due to the cost and complexity of expert annotation. Moreover, the use of contrastive learning on unlabeled data may act as an implicit regularization mechanism, encouraging the learning of more robust and generalizable feature representations. The proposed semi-supervised strategy was evaluated across three independent datasets, including an in-domain test set, a newly acquired clinical dataset collected at the same institution, and an external dataset from a different institution. In addition, an ablation study was conducted to analyze the impact of key design choices in the proposed framework. These experiments showed that activating the contrastive loss only after an initial supervised warm-up and using moderate data augmentation in the contrastive branch lead to more stable training and improved detection performance. Moreover, the experiment *Contr_pretrain* indicated that contrastive learning is most effective when applied directly within the detection framework, rather than as an independent pretraining step.

The proposed framework consistently improved detection performance compared to *Sup_baseline*, as shown in [Table 5a](#).

Qualitative results further highlight the benefits of leveraging unlabeled data, showing more stable detection behavior in challenging cases characterized by subtle lesion appearance, irregular morphology, variable illumination, and heterogeneous acquisition conditions ([Fig. 3](#)). In relatively straightforward examples, such as images with clear lesion boundaries and good visual contrast frequently observed in the GOA-1 dataset, both the supervised baseline and the proposed semi-supervised framework produce bounding boxes well aligned with the ground-truth annotations, suggesting that supervised learning alone may be sufficient when lesions are visually unambiguous. Differences

Table 6
Modality-specific comparison between the supervised baseline (*Sup_baseline*) and the proposed semi-supervised framework.

Dataset	Model	Modality	mAP@0.5	mAP@0.75	Precision	Recall
GOA-1 labeled	<i>Sup_baseline</i>	WL	54.96	18.47	77.88	46.21
	<i>Sup_baseline</i>	NBI	79.42	38.94	76.81	74.33
	Proposed framework	WL	60.98	24.67	68.52	56.82
	Proposed framework	NBI	85.04	43.69	82.11	81.63
ATH	<i>Sup_baseline</i>	WL	50.36	14.93	65.71	44.95
	<i>Sup_baseline</i>	NBI	43.34	10.76	53.27	39.61
	Proposed framework	WL	58.04	16.27	65.78	56.18
	Proposed framework	NBI	51.31	13.11	69.22	43.64
GOA-2	<i>Sup_baseline</i>	WL	63.94	42.05	78.65	53.82
	<i>Sup_baseline</i>	NBI	46.00	22.62	57.71	38.46
	Proposed framework	WL	62.77	36.00	65.52	58.43
	Proposed framework	NBI	53.70	23.86	72.27	42.59

Table 7
Comparison of the proposed framework against state-of-the-art supervised and semi-supervised object detectors.

Dataset	Model	Method	mAP@0.5	mAP@0.75	Precision	Recall
GOA-1	YOLOv5	Supervised	64.20	31.40	71.70	61.70
	YOLOv8		61.15	28.53	63.72	63.04
	RT-DETR		68.82	30.02	73.80	63.69
	DINO-DETR		64.68	22.80	70.56	65.00
	Unbiased-teacher	Semi-supervised	61.66	28.75	61.70	75.70
	Proposed framework		71.27	32.84	75.26	67.39
ATH	YOLOv5	Supervised	45.60	17.30	58.00	47.10
	YOLOv8		51.91	12.65	62.75	53.08
	RT-DETR		30.64	07.56	45.93	35.68
	DINO-DETR		54.42	13.94	68.16	57.00
	Unbiased-teacher	Semi-supervised	60.96	13.88	61.00	83.90
	Proposed framework		54.30	14.21	64.38	50.22
GOA-2	YOLOv5	Supervised	54.30	26.20	66.70	50.80
	YOLOv8		45.35	21.67	69.32	37.46
	RT-DETR		50.36	21.60	62.90	49.74
	DINO-DETR		50.44	24.81	65.97	49.00
	Unbiased-teacher	Semi-supervised	52.94	19.42	52.90	68.90
	Proposed framework		57.06	29.53	64.27	51.81

between the two approaches become more evident in clinically challenging scenarios. In cases involving elongated or irregular lesions, partial occlusions, limited contrast with surrounding tissue, or variability in endoscopic appearance across centers — more commonly observed in the GOA-2 and ATH datasets — the supervised baseline often produces incomplete, shifted, or imprecise detections. In contrast, the proposed semi-supervised framework more consistently localizes the pathological regions, generating bounding boxes that better match the spatial extent of the lesions and maintaining more stable behavior under heterogeneous imaging conditions. Nevertheless, both approaches may still exhibit limitations in particularly complex cases, such as images containing multiple lesions, ambiguous lesion boundaries, severe reflections, blood, saliva, or partial vocal fold visibility. In some examples, the proposed framework detects only part of the pathological region or generates less precise localization, while in other isolated cases the supervised baseline correctly detects lesions missed by the semi-supervised model. These failure cases generally correspond to visually ambiguous scenarios with substantial endoscopic artifacts or atypical lesion appearance.

Overall, the qualitative analysis suggests that the proposed semi-supervised framework is generally more robust to variability in imaging conditions and endoscopic artifacts. This behavior may be attributed to the contrastive learning strategy applied on additional unlabeled endoscopic data, which exposes the model to a broader range of visual patterns during training. However, extreme cases characterized by dominant artifacts or severe occlusions may still negatively affect the patch mining process, occasionally leading the model to focus

on visually salient but clinically irrelevant regions. Unlike pseudo-labeling-based semi-supervised strategies, the proposed framework did not introduce additional supervision signals derived from model predictions. This design choice avoided potential error accumulation from incorrect pseudo-labels and preserves a clear separation between the supervised detection objective and the self-supervised representation-learning component. Consequently, integrating contrastive learning enhances robustness without increasing inference complexity or altering the deployment pipeline.

An important aspect of the proposed framework is its ability to improve generalization beyond the training distribution, as demonstrated by the results obtained on the GOA-2 and ATH datasets, with mAP@0.5 improvements of +4.15 and +8.18 points, respectively. Although the GOA-2 dataset was acquired at the same clinical center as the training data, it was collected at a later time point and involved different clinical personnel, introducing variability in acquisition conditions and examination practices. The ATH dataset represents an even more challenging domain shift, as it was collected at a different institution in another country and includes examinations performed by multiple clinicians using different acquisition settings. This variability is further reflected in the t-SNE visualization shown in Fig. 4, where ATH images occupy a more distinct region of the embedding space compared to GOA-1 labeled and GOA-2 samples. Despite these differences, the proposed semi-supervised framework consistently outperformed supervised training across datasets, suggesting that the learned feature representations are more robust to variations in imaging conditions, acquisition protocols, and clinical practice. These findings support the potential of

the proposed approach for developing computer-assisted systems that generalize more reliably across heterogeneous real-world clinical environments. The observed increase in recall across datasets (+6.21 and +9.91 percentage points on the GOA-2 and ATH datasets, respectively) is particularly relevant from a clinical perspective, as false-negative detections during SCC screening may delay further diagnostic assessment and treatment planning. By improving detection sensitivity in routine outpatient endoscopic examinations, the proposed framework may support earlier identification of suspicious lesions and facilitate more timely referral for histopathological confirmation and clinical management.

As detailed in Table 7, the benchmark against state-of-the-art object detectors offers valuable insights into the relationship between model architecture, learning paradigms, and clinical generalization. First, the proposed semi-supervised approach consistently achieves higher mAP@0.5 values than both YOLOv5 and YOLOv8 models commonly used in the literature across all evaluated datasets, while also providing comparable or improved recall. This suggests that the gains obtained with our framework primarily derive from the proposed contrastive training strategy, rather than merely from differences in model architecture. While standard YOLOv5 and YOLOv8 show competitive performance on the in-domain GOA-1 labeled test set, their results degrade more substantially on the external ATH dataset. In contrast, our proposed framework maintains more consistent performance across datasets. This improved robustness under domain shift aligns directly with the aim of the semi-supervised strategy, which leverages unlabeled data to learn representations that are less sensitive to dataset-specific biases.

A similar vulnerability to domain shift is observed in transformer-based architectures, such as RT-DETR and DINO-DETR. While these models show competitive results on the in-domain GOA-1 dataset, they exhibit a significant performance degradation when evaluated on the external ATH cohort (e.g., RT-DETR's mAP@0.5 drops to 30.64). This behavior is characteristic of vision transformers, which generally require massive datasets to learn domain-invariant features.

Furthermore, comparing different semi-supervised paradigms reveals a clear trade-off between sensitivity and specificity. The Unbiased-teacher framework, which relies on a pseudo-labeling strategy, achieves the highest recall across all evaluation datasets, peaking at 83.90% on the ATH dataset. This high sensitivity is typical of teacher-student architectures that reinforce high-confidence predictions. However, this comes at the cost of a marked decrease in precision compared to our approach. By leveraging contrastive learning as an implicit regularization mechanism our model avoids the confirmation bias typical of self-training methods. This results in a superior balance, yielding the highest mAP@0.5 on both GOA-1 and GOA-2 while consistently outperforming Unbiased-teacher in precision.

Future work may investigate the integration of additional optimization strategies within the proposed semi-supervised framework, such as architectural enhancements designed to improve detection of small or low-contrast lesions. In particular, the incorporation of decoupled super-resolution branches, as proposed in [4], could be investigated to further enhance feature quality during training.

The most closely related work to the present approach in terms of methodology is [25], where a contrastive learning framework for fine-grained classification of laryngeal leukoplakia is proposed. Their method leverages contrastive learning for image-level classification of NBI frames under limited annotation settings, and does not explicitly address lesion localization. Moreover, leukoplakia often shows strong visual contrast in WL imaging, whereas early-stage laryngeal SCC may be characterized by less evident morphological and vascular patterns, particularly in NBI, posing additional challenges for lesion localization. As a result, the interpretability of the model outputs is limited to coarse attention maps, without providing explicit spatial predictions that can directly support visual assessment during endoscopic examinations. In contrast, the present work focuses on lesion detection, enabling explicit

localization of pathological regions while exploiting unlabeled data within a unified detection framework. This explicit localization may improve clinical interpretability compared to image-level classification approaches, as clinicians can directly visualize the regions contributing to the model prediction during endoscopic assessment. The importance of interpretable AI systems in clinical decision support has also been highlighted in other medical applications, including gastrointestinal disease diagnosis [33] and neurological disease assessment [34,35].

Regarding computational efficiency, the proposed method introduces overhead during the training phase. As shown in Table 5b, training time increases by approximately 2.4 times, and the parameter count is higher due to the dual-branch architecture. However, we argue that this trade-off is highly advantageous for practical clinical application. The additional computational cost is strictly confined to the offline training phase. At deployment time, the contrastive branch is discarded, meaning the model retains the lightweight architecture and real-time inference speed (approx. 6.4 GFLOPs) of the standard YOLOv11n baseline. Consequently, the framework achieves significant improvements in robustness and generalization without compromising the real-time processing capabilities strictly required for live endoscopic examinations.

Despite the encouraging results, this study has some limitations that should be considered when interpreting our findings. First, all datasets included in this work consist exclusively of images from patients with histologically confirmed SCC. Future studies could extend this framework to include other clinically relevant lesion types, such as high-risk lesions (e.g., leukoplakia) as well as low-risk conditions (e.g., polyps or Reinke's edema), enabling a more comprehensive assessment across a broader spectrum of laryngeal pathologies. Nevertheless, the datasets considered in this study represent one of the largest collections of annotated endoscopic examinations for laryngeal SCC reported to date, in terms of patient count and video data, supporting the validity of the reported results despite the focus on SCC cases.

Second, the analysis was performed at the frame level, without explicitly exploiting the temporal information available in endoscopic video sequences. While frame-based detection offers a practical, computationally efficient approach, incorporating temporal context can further improve robustness and reduce false detections, particularly in challenging cases affected by motion, blur, or partial visibility of the vocal folds. Future work could extend the proposed framework toward video-level analysis by incorporating lesion tracking across consecutive endoscopic frames, potentially leveraging recent foundation models for segmentation and tracking, such as the Segment Anything Model (SAM) [36], to enforce temporal consistency of detected regions. In addition, future studies will focus on validating the framework on more heterogeneous clinical cohorts, including benign and pre-malignant laryngeal lesions in addition to SCC, in order to further assess the robustness, specificity, and clinical applicability of the proposed approach under more diverse real-world screening conditions.

6. Conclusion

In this work, we presented a semi-supervised learning framework for laryngeal SCC detection in endoscopic images that integrates contrastive representation learning into a single-stage object detection architecture. The proposed approach enables the effective use of routinely acquired unlabeled clinical data during training while preserving a standard and computationally efficient inference pipeline.

Experimental evaluation on multiple datasets, including a prospective cohort and an external multi-center dataset, demonstrated consistent improvements over supervised training across both white-light and narrow-band imaging modalities. In particular, the proposed framework showed improved robustness and generalization under heterogeneous acquisition conditions and across different clinical centers.

From a clinical perspective, improving the sensitivity and robustness of SCC detection in routine outpatient endoscopic examinations may

support earlier identification of suspicious lesions and facilitate timely referral for histopathological assessment and treatment planning. In addition, the explicit localization of pathological regions may improve the interpretability of model predictions and provide more intuitive visual support for clinicians during endoscopic evaluation.

Overall, these findings suggest that semi-supervised learning strategies represent a promising direction for the development of more reliable and clinically applicable computer-assisted decision-support systems for laryngeal cancer assessment in real-world practice.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Daniela De Luca: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Lorenzo Federici:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization, Methodology. **Maria Chiara Fiorentino:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Claudio Sampieri:** Visualization, Resources, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Francesco Mora:** Data curation. **Giorgio Peretti:** Data curation. **Elisa Bellini:** Data curation. **Athanasios C. Sakellariadis:** Data curation. **Andriana Razou:** Data curation. **Georgios P. Kotsis:** Data curation. **Leonardo S. De Mattos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Sara Moccia:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by the Horizon Europe project AIRCARE, GA no. 101137426. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] A. Koroulakis, M. Agarwal, Laryngeal cancer, in: StatPearls [Internet], StatPearls Publishing, 2024.
- [2] N. Davaris, S. Voigt-Zimmermann, S. Kropf, C. Arens, Flexible transnasal endoscopy with white light or narrow band imaging for the diagnosis of laryngeal malignancy: diagnostic value, observer variability and influence of previous laryngeal surgery, *Eur. Arch. Otorhinolaryngol.* 276 (2) (2019) 459–466.
- [3] M. Filairo, A. Vallin, M. Fragale, C. Sampieri, L. Guastini, F. Mora, G. Peretti, Office-based procedures in laryngology, *Acta Otorhinolaryngol. Ital.* 41 (3) (2020) 243.
- [4] C. Baldini, L. Migliorelli, D. Berardini, M.A. Azam, C. Sampieri, A. Ioppi, R. Srivastava, G. Peretti, L.S. Mattos, Improving real-time detection of laryngeal lesions in endoscopic images using a decoupled super-resolution enhanced YOLO, *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.* 260 (2025) 108539.
- [5] L. Maier-Hein, M. Eisenmann, D. Sarikaya, K. März, T. Collins, A. Malpani, J. Fallert, H. Feussner, S. Giannarou, P. Mascagni, et al., Surgical data science—from concepts toward clinical translation, *Med. Image Anal.* 76 (2022) 102306.
- [6] S. Moccia, E. De Momi, M. Guarnaschelli, M. Savazzi, A. Laborai, L. Guastini, G. Peretti, L.S. Mattos, Confident texture-based laryngeal tissue classification for early stage diagnosis support, *J. Med. Imaging* 4 (3) (2017) 034502–034502.
- [7] C. Sampieri, C. Baldini, M.A. Azam, S. Moccia, L.S. Mattos, I. Vilaseca, G. Peretti, A. Ioppi, Artificial intelligence for upper aerodigestive tract endoscopy and laryngoscopy: a guide for physicians and state-of-the-art review, *Otolaryngology–Head Neck Surg.* 169 (4) (2023) 811–829.
- [8] T. Araujo, C.P. Santos, E. De Momi, S. Moccia, Learned and handcrafted features for early-stage laryngeal scc diagnosis, *Med. Biol. Eng. Comput.* 57 (12) (2019) 2683–2692.
- [9] B.A. Tran, T.T.P. Dao, H.D.Q. Dung, N.B. Van, C.C. Ha, N.H. Pham, T.C.H.T.N. Cam, T.-C. Nguyen, M.-K. Pham, M.-K. Tran, et al., Support of deep learning to classify vocal fold images in flexible laryngoscopy, *Am. J. Otolaryngol.* 44 (3) (2023) 103800.
- [10] Z.-H. Xu, D.-G. Fan, J.-Q. Huang, J.-W. Wang, Y. Wang, Y.-Z. Li, Computer-aided diagnosis of laryngeal cancer based on deep learning with laryngoscopic images, *Diagnostics* 13 (24) (2023) 3669.
- [11] A.R. Marrero-Gonzalez, T.J. Diemer, S.A. Nguyen, T.J. Camilon, K. Meenan, A. O'Rourke, Application of artificial intelligence in laryngeal lesions: a systematic review and meta-analysis, *Eur. Arch. Otorhinolaryngol.* 282 (3) (2025) 1543–1555.
- [12] B. Luan, Y. Sun, C. Tong, Y. Liu, H. Liu, R-FCN based laryngeal lesion detection, in: International Symposium on Computational Intelligence and Design, Vol. 2, IEEE, 2019, pp. 128–131.
- [13] D.J. Wellenstein, J. Woodburn, H.A. Marres, G.B. van den Broek, Detection of laryngeal carcinoma during endoscopy using artificial intelligence, *Head & Neck* 45 (9) (2023) 2217–2226.
- [14] G.H. Kim, Y.J. Hwang, H. Lee, E.-S. Sung, K.W. Nam, Convolutional neural network-based vocal cord tumor classification technique for home-based self-prescreening purpose, *BioMedical Eng. OnLine* 22 (1) (2023) 81.
- [15] M.A. Azam, C. Sampieri, A. Ioppi, S. Africano, A. Vallin, D. Moccia, M. Fragale, L. Guastini, S. Moccia, C. Piazza, et al., Deep learning applied to white light and narrow band imaging videolaryngoscopy: toward real-time laryngeal cancer detection, *Laryngoscope* 132 (9) (2022) 1798–1806.
- [16] M.J. Kim, S.H. Kim, S.M. Kim, J.H. Nam, Y.B. Hwang, Y.J. Lim, The advent of domain adaptation into artificial intelligence for gastrointestinal endoscopy and medical imaging, *Diagnostics* 13 (19) (2023) 3023.
- [17] L. Qu, S. Liu, X. Liu, M. Wang, Z. Song, Towards label-efficient automatic diagnosis and analysis: a comprehensive survey of advanced deep learning-based weakly-supervised, semi-supervised and self-supervised techniques in histopathological image analysis, *Phys. Med. Biol.* 67 (20) (2022) 20TR01.
- [18] W. Zhang, L. Zhu, J. Hallinan, S. Zhang, A. Makmur, Q. Cai, B.C. Ooi, Boostmis: Boosting medical image semi-supervised learning with adaptive pseudo labeling and informative active annotation, in: IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2022, pp. 20666–20676.
- [19] H. Basak, Z. Yin, Pseudo-label guided contrastive learning for semi-supervised medical image segmentation, in: IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2023, pp. 19786–19797.
- [20] T. Chen, S. Kornblith, M. Norouzi, G. Hinton, A simple framework for contrastive learning of visual representations, in: International Conference on Machine Learning, PMLR, 2020, pp. 1597–1607.
- [21] K. He, H. Fan, Y. Wu, S. Xie, R. Girshick, Momentum contrast for unsupervised visual representation learning, in: IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2020, pp. 9729–9738.
- [22] K. Chaitanya, E. Erdil, N. Karani, E. Konukoglu, Contrastive learning of global and local features for medical image segmentation with limited annotations, *Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.* 33 (2020) 12546–12558.
- [23] G. Migliorelli, M.C. Fiorentino, M. Di Cosmo, F.P. Villani, A. Mancini, S. Moccia, On the use of contrastive learning for standard-plane classification in fetal ultrasound imaging, *Comput. Biol. Med.* 174 (2024) 108430.
- [24] M.C. Fiorentino, G. Migliorelli, F.P. Villani, E. Frontoni, S. Moccia, Contrastive prototype federated learning against noisy labels in fetal standard plane detection, *Int. J. Comput. Assist. Radiol. Surg.* (2025) 1–9.
- [25] Z. You, B. Han, Z. Shi, S. Du, M. Zhao, Z. Lv, X. Hei, H. Liu, X. Ren, Y. Yan, Single-view contrastive learning for laryngeal leukoplakia classification with NBI laryngoscopy images, *Head & Neck* (2025).
- [26] M.G. Ragab, S.J. Abdulkadir, A. Muneer, A. Alqushaibi, E.H. Sumiea, R. Qureshi, S.M. Al-Selwi, H. Alhussian, A comprehensive systematic review of YOLO for medical object detection (2018 to 2023), *IEEE Access* 12 (2024) 57815–57836.
- [27] G. Jocher, J. Qiu, Ultralytics YOLO11, 2024, [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>.
- [28] C. Baldini, M.A. Azam, C. Sampieri, A. Ioppi, L. Ruiz-Sevilla, I. Vilaseca, B. Alegre, A. Tirrito, A. Pennacchi, G. Peretti, et al., An automated approach for real-time informative frames classification in laryngeal endoscopy using deep learning, *Eur. Arch. Otorhinolaryngol.* 281 (8) (2024) 4255–4264.
- [29] S. Surapaneni, R.B. Kutler, S.A. Setzen, Y.E. Kim, P. Yao, S.H. Siddiqui, M.J. Pitman, L. Sulica, O. Elemento, P. Khosravi, et al., A multimodal approach for deep-learning classification of vocal fold pathologies in stroboscopy, *Laryngoscope* (2026).
- [30] Y. Zhao, W. Lv, S. Xu, J. Wei, G. Wang, Q. Dang, Y. Liu, J. Chen, Detrs beat yolos on real-time object detection, in: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2024, pp. 16965–16974.

- [31] H. Zhang, F. Li, S. Liu, L. Zhang, H. Su, J. Zhu, L. Ni, H.-Y. Shum, DINO: DETR with improved DeNoising anchor boxes for end-to-end object detection, in: The Eleventh International Conference on Learning Representations.
- [32] Y.-C. Liu, C.-Y. Ma, Z. He, C.-W. Kuo, K. Chen, P. Zhang, B. Wu, Z. Kira, P. Vajda, Unbiased teacher for semi-supervised object detection, 2021, arXiv:2102.09480 [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2102.09480>.
- [33] M.J. Abbas, H. Alshaya, W. Bouchelligua, N. Hassan, I.M. Nasir, Hierarchical multi-stage attention and dynamic expert routing for explainable gastrointestinal disease diagnosis, *Diagnostics* 15 (21) (2025) 2714.
- [34] M.J. Abbas, M.A. Khan, A. Hamza, S. Alsenan, A. Rehman, J. Baili, Y. Zhang, C3BAM-XAI: convolutional block attention module enhanced explainable artificial intelligence-based parkinson's disease stage classification, *Cogn. Comput.* 17 (3) (2025) 111.
- [35] M.J. Abbas, M.A. Khan, A. Hussain, S. Ayouni, M. Maddeh, F. Alhayan, Xrdnet: a novel explainable residual dense fusion network for alzheimer's disease recognition from MRI images, *Cogn. Comput.* 17 (6) (2025) 174.
- [36] A. Kirillov, E. Mintun, N. Ravi, H. Mao, C. Rolland, L. Gustafson, T. Xiao, S. Whitehead, A.C. Berg, W.-Y. Lo, P. Dollár, R. Girshick, Segment anything, 2023, arXiv preprint arXiv:2304.02643.